

Effect of Leadership Approach to Organizational Commitment: A Study in Transportation Sector

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Abstract—Employees commitments of vision and mission of organization is effected due to manager's executes by approach of leadership. The leaders who have attributions like vision, confidence and correctness, sharing and participation, creativeness, progressive learning –improvement and responsibility are effective to increase organizational commitment if they are sensitive to expectation and requirement of employees in an organization. Studies about organizational commitment appear results that employees who have strong organizational commitment have the most contribution. In this study, "Leadership" and "Organizational Commitment" conduct surveys to 31 employees of Ahmet Özdemir Nak. Tic. San. A.Ş. which has operations in road and railway transportation sector. It is analyzed the effects of leadership approach to organizational commitment deals with result of survey.

Keywords—Leadership Approach, Organizational Commitment, Study

I. INTRODUCTION

EMPLOYERS try to achieve the objectives in accordance with their mission and vision. In the globalized and dominated by increasing competition and new technologies new era, enterprises need employees committed to the leader and organization, to achieve their objectives of making profit and providing continuity. Leadership approach adopted by the leader, employees' motivation, their organizational commitment, professional development, has a significant impact on job satisfaction and communication skills. Different definitions have been made on leadership by different authors. Pioneer, is the person who have the power to have something done by making others request and consider it [1]. Vision, trust, honesty, sharing and participation, creativity, continuous learning and improvement, and responsibility are the concepts in the effective leaders manual [2]. Today, when the competitive environment brought about by globalization become more apparent, managers and employees' expectations and demands has led to the emergence of new approaches in the field of leadership. Basically there are five different leadership approaches:

Transformational Leadership: Transformational leadership is based on the hypothesis of encouraging creativity. For this reason, employees will be helped to get creative [3]. It is the form of leadership to develop a sudden and effective change in the organization. It is the combination of skills that will allow leaders to start up the change efficiently, create the foresight to guide this change and identify the need for change [4].

Transactional Leadership: Leader, do not put in an effort to develop his subordinates' personal values or ensure their trust in himself. Instead, they take into account the needs of subordinates and try to satisfy their needs when the subordinates have reached a predetermined level of performance [5]. Transactional leaders are the leaders who least support deliberates change [6]. Transactional leadership is based on a process of exchange in which subordinates are offered prices by their leaders and leaders receive in return their performance and the efforts [7].

Autocratic Leadership: Autocratic leaders take all the decisions themselves, by not transferring the authority and responsibility, and do not allow subordinates to participate in decision-making process. Enterprises managed in this style, accelerate decision-making processes, but the team spirit does not occur, trust and cooperation cannot be ensured [8].

Participatory Leadership: Listening is the key point for participatory leadership style. Participating leaders can work as a team member more than a leader in superior-subordinate relationship. Participating leaders have skills to harmonize and appease confusions within the team [9].

Liberalization Based Leadership: In groups where leaders are liberal, decisions are taken by the group, leaders don't interfere with the followers work, authority and power pass to the follower and followers direct the group and the leader [10].

It is suggested that; individuals who demonstrate commitment to the organization, increase productivity, efficiency, and act responsibly. An employee committed to the organization, strongly believes in the aims and values, and expectations; willingly complies with the orders [11]. When definitions about the organizational commitment are examined, it is seen that organizational commitment is defined as loyalty, to making sacrifices for the organization, adopting the objectives of the organization, adopting the self-organization, participating in the activities of the organization and a positive contribution to the organization [12].

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It is known that; converter and transactional leaders and positive changes in behavior of processes, positively effects organizational commitment of organization members; and leaders' contribution to the social lives of members of the organization, is known to increase the allegiance of members of the organization to the leaders, and therefore the organization [13]. It is argued that; charismatic leadership behavior, which is a dimension of transformational leadership, benefits from identification internalization concepts in employees' adoption in organizational goals and values. Employee in size of this commitment means to have adopted to stay in the organization and to strive to achieve the objectives of the organization [14].

II. ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

Organizational commitment as a, the strength of the bond that employee feel about the organization that arise as a result of organization-employee relationship. In other words, organizational commitment which represent the the psychological approach to the organization is a psychological condition that reflects the relationship between the employee and the organization, and that led to the decision to continue membership in the organization [15], [16].

According to Eisenberg and others, the concept of organizational commitment involves three elements. These elements are [17]:

- Adoption of the Organization's goals and values and feeling a strong belief in these values,
- Spend more effort than expected, to maintain the organization's benefit,
- Feeling a strong desire to continue membership in the organization.

The common features of definitions related to the concept of organizational commitment is the expectation for the individuals connected to the organization to behave in the direction of doing their best for providing the success of the the organization. However, the idea about strong committed employees to have higher performance levels than the ones without commitment is the most important factor used as a base in defining the organizational commitment concept [18]. Meyer and Allen have examined organizational commitment, in three dimensions as; affective commitment, continuance and normative commitment [19]. Emotional commitment is defined as the desire of individuals working in the enterprise to remain in the enterprise with their own preferences. Continuance commitment is the employees' taking into account cost of leaving their work and continuing in the enterprise as an obligation. Normative commitment, is the feeling of the employees connected to the organization as a moral sense of duty and because they believe they should not leave the enterprise [15]. The common feature of these three commitment type (affective, continuance and normative), that they reflect psychological condition which connect the employees to an organization and which effect the decisions about whether the slidatary with the organization wil continue or not [20], [21].

III. MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this study, profile of participants will be identified primarily by using the frequency analysis of demographic characteristics. After taking the mean and standard deviation of the questions about organizational commitment and the leadership style of managers; and due diligence is done, reliability analysis of the bilateral questions will be performed. The inter-relationship among multi-factor leadership variables and organizational commitment will be determined and analyzed by correlation analysis.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Descriptive Statistics Analysis on Demographic Characteristics

In the survey used in this study, questions on years of work in the current position, educational status, total working years and working years in the institution have been asked to determine the demographic characteristics of survey respondents. The results obtained from frequency analysis of the variables are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 ANALYSIS OF DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS ON THE FREQUENCY AND PERCENT

		Frequency	Percent %
Working years in the position	1-3 Years	14	45,2
	4-7 Years	7	22,6
	8-11 Years	5	16,1
	12 and more	5	16,1
Educational status	Elementary	10	32,3
	High School	16	51,6
	VHS	1	3,2
	University	4	12,9
Age	18-25	1	3,2
	26-30	6	19,4
	31-35	11	35,5
	36 and older	13	41,9
Working time in the institution	1-3 Years	23	74,2
	4-7 Years	5	16,1
	8-11 Years	2	6,5
	12 and more	1	3,2
Total working time	1-3 Years	15	48,4
	4-7 Years	10	32,3
	8-11 Years	1	3,2
	12 and more	5	16,1

Constituting the majority of those surveyed 45.2% ', have worked in the current position for 1-3 years. 22.6% of the participants' have worked for 4-7 years, 16.1% of them 8-11 years, and finally 16.1% over 12 years in the current positions. 51.6% of respondents' assessed high school graduates; 32.3% of them elementary school graduates, 12.9% university graduates and 3.2% is determined as the Vocational High School graduates for the educational status question. 41.9% of employees surveyed are older than 36 years. 31-35 age groups, forms the 35.5% of the participants.

While 19.4% of the participants are in 26-30 age groups, 3.2% of them are in 18-25 age group. While 74.2%, a large group of the participants' working time in the institution is 1-3 years, 16.1% of them have worked 4-7 years in the institution. 6.5%, have worked 8-11 years, and 3.2% have worked over 12 years. When the total working duration of the participants in the agency is analyzed, 48.4% of employees' working life of is 1-3 years. 32.3% of them are the second position in quantity with 4-7 years of experience. While 16% have 12 years and above experience, the 3.2% have 8-11 years experience.

B. Descriptive Statistics: Analysis of Leadership Behavior and Organizational Commitment Variables

In the research, 36 variables related to leadership style were evaluated in a scale of five in the 1 Never 2 Rarely, 3 Sometimes 4 Most of the time 5 Always format. 15 variables related to organizational commitment are evaluated in likert scale of between 1-strongly disagree and 5-strongly agree. The average standard deviation values for each variable are shown in Table II and Table III.

TABLE II
LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR VARIABLES' MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
F1 Helps me only when he/she sees my effort.	30	4,03	1,38
F2 Reviews the appropriateness of the critical decisions.	30	4,33	0,71
F3 Does not interfere before problems become serious.	30	4,03	1,10
F4 His/her attention is on errors, inaccuracies and non-conformities.	31	1,68	0,98
F5 When an important issue comes up refrains from interfering.	31	1,65	1,02
F6 Shares values and beliefs which are important for him/her with us.	30	4,00	1,11
F7 It is difficult to reach him when needed.	31	1,71	1,22
F8 Searches for different perspectives when solving problems.	30	4,17	0,91
F9 Has optimistic view of future and positive conversations.	30	4,27	0,83
F10 People are proud to work with him/her.	30	4,37	0,89
F11 When we reach performance goals, provides rewards.	30	4,23	0,94
F12 Things should get worse and worse, for him/her to take action.	30	1,53	0,86
F13 Tells our goals to reach in a great enthusiasm.	30	4,03	0,96
F14 Highlights the importance of having a strong purpose.	30	4,27	0,83
F15 Spends time to train employees and teach them new things.	30	4,13	0,82
F16 Learn what are the expectations of employees and clearly indicates what he/she is waiting for.	30	4,13	0,94
F17 Believes it to be unnecessary to get action unless it is seriously necessary to get action.	31	1,84	1,10
F18 Sacrifices his /her own priority for the group's good.	30	4,00	1,02
F19 Treats to employees not as any member of the group but as an individual.	30	4,17	0,83
F20 Problems should get chronicle for him/het to take action.	31	1,81	1,11
F21 His/her behavior allows employees to respect him.	30	4,10	0,84
F22 Spend his/her time looking for problems that require urgent intervention.	31	1,74	1,12
F23 Considers the moral and ethical consequences of his/her decisions.	30	4,10	0,88
F24 Never forgets errors, investigates until he/she finds who is responsible for it.	31	1,74	1,12
F25 Creates a sense of power and trust in employees.	30	4,33	0,80

F26 Effects the employees with his/her vision for the future.	30	4,30	0,92
F27 Pay attention to reduce errors and failures, to achieve standards.	31	4,23	1,06
F28 Avoids deciding.	30	1,50	0,78
F29 Approaches employees as individuals with different needs and abilities.	30	4,17	1,05
F30 Recommends employees to look at work from different perspectives.	30	4,23	1,17
F31 Creates opportunities for employees to develop themselves and supports them.	30	4,17	0,95
F32 Recommends new perspectives toe employees on how to do tasks.	31	2,23	1,50
F33 Delays to answer emergent questions.	30	3,87	1,43
F34 Highlights the importance of having a common understanding of the mission task.	30	4,23	1,04
F35 Appreciate the employees when they do a good job.	30	4,40	0,97
F36 Creates confidence in the targets will be met.	30	4,50	0,78

According to Table II, according to information received from survey respondents average level of Managers' Leadership Behavior Variables varies between levels of 1.50 and 4.50.

TABLE III
THE AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE ORGANIZATION COMMITMENT VARIABLES

	N	Mean	Std.Dev.
F1 I'm willing to strive on doing what is expected from me for the company to succeed.	31	4,68	0,75
F2 I tell to my friends that this establishment is a great place to work in.	31	4,42	0,67
F3 I feel very little loyalty to this establishment.	31	1,52	1,03
F4 I am ready to accept every task given to continue working in this establishment.	31	4,29	0,86
F5 I find the establishments' values very similar to my personal values.	31	4,23	1,06
F6 I'm proud to say to others that I am an employee of this establishment	31	4,35	0,80
F7 I can also work in another workplace as long as it is a similar one in nature.	31	4,19	1,38
F8 This establishment provides me to introduce my performance in the best way.	31	4,48	0,77
F9 Even a small change in the existing workplace may result my leaving.	31	1,45	1,03
F10 When I think of the first time I came to the workplace, I'm happy to have chosen the current workplace rather than the others.	31	4,52	0,93
F11 Staying in this workplace is of no avail to me in the long run.	31	1,23	0,67
F12 I often do not approve the attitudes of the establishment towards key issues related to the staff.	31	1,48	1,09
F13 It is really important for me, what this workplace will happen in the future.	31	4,03	1,20
F14 Here is the best workplace to me among the workplaces where I can work.	31	4,16	0,82
F15 This is a complete mistake for me to decide to work in this workplace.	31	1,32	0,87

According to Table III, Variables Mean of research participants' Commitment to the Organization varies with the level between the level of 1.23 and 4.68.

C. Dimensions of Leadership Behavior Variables

Calculations were made according to information obtained from the literature. In the question survey of 36 questions in total, 20 items are about transformational leadership, 12 items are about transactional leader, 4 items are about liberal leadership styles [22]. The dimensions in Sayin's master's thesis [22] can be summarized as follows.

In the survey, sub-factors determining transformational leadership style are number 2, 6, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 21, 23, 25, 26, 29, 30, 31, 32, 34, 36, expressions and they consist of 20 items. Sub-factors that determine transactional leader are number 1, 3, 4, 11, 12, 16, 17, 20, 22, 24, 27, 35, expressions and they consist of 12 items. Sub-factors about liberal leader are in 5, 7, 28, 33, numbered expressions. The mean and standard deviation for each dimension is given by Table IV.

TABLE IV
MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE DIMENSIONS OF LEADERSHIP STYLE

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Transformational Leadership	31	4,03	0,78
Transactional Leadership	31	3,04	0,52
Liberal Leadership	31	2,16	0,68

Transformational leadership is significantly high 4.03, Transactional Leadership medium 3.04, recognition of freedom is low-level 2.16. "In business transformational leadership approach is applied." has been concluded.

D. Dimensions of Commitment to the Organization Variables

Organization Commitment Scale consists of two sub-factors. Expression of sub-factor where Commitment to the Organization is high is Commitment to the Organization 1, and expression of sub-factor where the Commitment to the Organization is high poor, is Commitment to the Organization 2. [22]. Sayın has shown the two variables about commitment to the organization as follows:

Sub-factor for commitment to the organization 1 is numbered in clauses 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 13, 14. Sub-factor for commitment to the organization 2 is numbered in clauses 3, 7, 9, 11, 12, 15. Mean and standard deviation of each dimension are given in Table V.

TABLE V
MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE DIMENSIONS OF COMMITMENT TO THE ORGANIZATION

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Commitment to the Organization 1	31	4,35	0,69
Commitment to the Organization 2	31	1,87	0,63

While Commitment to the Organization 1 which is the expression the sub-factor of higher level of Commitment to the Organization was 4.35 with a high commitment to the organization; While Commitment to the Organization 2 which is the expression the sub-factor of lower level of Commitment to the Organization was significantly low with a level of 1.87.

E. Difference Analysis of the Dimensions of Leadership Behavior by Demographic Characteristics

It was tested by one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) test if there was significant difference according to the variables of; working time in the position, educational status, age, working time in the institution, total working time,

in the research work where all three dimensions of leadership behavior dealt with. Although it was asked as working times in the position, institution and as total, the calculations of current position were used because all three results are the same.

Hypothesis: Leadership behavior dimensions vary according to demographic characteristics.

Each demographic characteristics and the size of hypothesis are given in Table VI, VII and VIII as a result of the analysis.

TABLE VI
RESULTS OF DIVERSITY ANALYSIS OF WORKING BY DURATION OF THE DIMENSIONS OF LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR

		N	Mean	F	p
Transformational Leadership	1-3 Years	14	3,95	0,11	0,95
	4-7 Years	7	4,06		
	8-11 Years	5	4,05		
	12 and more	5	4,19		
Transactional Leadership	1-3 Years	14	3,10	0,25	0,86
	4-7 Years	7	2,99		
	8-11 Years	5	3,11		
	12 and more	5	2,87		
Liberal Leadership	1-3 Years	14	2,32	0,91	0,45
	4-7 Years	7	2,25		
	8-11 Years	5	1,95		
	12 and more	5	1,80		

There was no significant difference in the position in three dimensions, according to working time. According Anova results, indicate values of p corresponding F values, respectively, $p = 0.95$, $p = 0.86$ and $p = 0.45$, and in 95% confidence interval test value which is greater than 0.05, so hypothesis has been.

TABLE VII
DIVERSITY ANALYSIS RESULTS OF DIMENSIONS OF LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR BY EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT

		N	Mean	F	p
Transformational Leadership	Elementary	10	4,12	3,61	0,03
	High School	16	3,98		
	VHS	1	2,00		
	University	4	4,53		
Transactional Leadership	Elementary	10	3,14	5,24	0,01
	High School	16	3,07		
	VHS	1	1,33		
	University	4	3,07		
Liberal Leadership	Elementary	10	2,15	0,45	0,72
	High School	16	2,25		
	VHS	1	1,50		
	University	4	2,00		

While transformational leadership behavior and transactional leadership behavior differ by educational status, liberal leadership does not differ.

Because $F = 3i61$ and $p = 0.03 < 0.05$ in transformational leadership; in the elementary school and university is very high with a rank of 4, in high school is very close to high with a rank of 3.98, and in VHS is significantly low with a rank of 2. In transactional leadership because $F = 5.24$ and $p = 0.01$, while in elementary school, high school and university graduates it is evaluated near 3, in VHS a very low evaluation has been made with a rank of 1,33. Evaluation is the same in liberal leadership and it is very low in all educational situations.

TABLE VIII
DIVERSITY ANALYSIS RESULTS OF DIMENSIONS OF LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR BY AGE

		N	Mean	F	P
Transformational Leadership	18-25	1	4,89	4,134	0,016
	26-30	6	3,20		
	31-35	11	4,29		
	36 and more	13	4,13		
Transactional Leadership	18-25	1	2,73	2,187	0,113
	26-30	6	2,77		
	31-35	11	3,33		
	36 and more	13	2,94		
Liberal Leadership	18-25	1	1,50	1,511	0,234
	26-30	6	2,63		
	31-35	11	2,00		
	36 and more	13	2,13		

Because in transformational leadership $F = 4.134$ and $p = 0.016 < 0.05$ there is vary according to age. Assessment of transformational leadership was low between the ages of 26-30. There is no significant difference in the other two dimensions.

F. Diversity Analysis of the Dimensions of Commitment to the Organization According to Demographic Characteristics

It was tested if there is difference between in commitment to the organization according to the demographic variables by a one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA). Although it was asked as working times in the position, institution and as total, the calculations of current position were used because all three results are the same.

TABLE IX
DIVERSITY ANALYSIS OF THE DIMENSIONS OF COMMITMENT TO THE ORGANIZATION BY DURATION OF WORK RESULTS

		N	Mean	F	p
Commitment to the Organization 1	1-3 Years	14	4,39	0,09	0,97
	4-7 Years	7	4,24		
	8-11 Years	5	4,33		
	12 and more	5	4,42		
Commitment to the Organization 2	1-3 Years	14	1,96	0,89	0,46
	4-7 Years	7	1,83		
	8-11 Years	5	2,03		
	12 and more	5	1,47		

Diversity Analysis of the Dimensions of Commitment to the Organization by working time was made with one-sided analysis of variance and F-values indicate that; because the corresponding values of p is greater than 0.05, commitment to the organization remain the same regardless of working time.

TABLE X
RESULTS OF DIVERSITY ANALYSIS OF DIMENSIONS OF COMMITMENT TO THE ORGANIZATION BY EDUCATIONAL STATUS

		N	Mean	F	P
Commitment to the Organization 1	Elementary	10	4,51	1,35	0,28
	High School	16	4,13		
	VHS	1	4,44		
	University	4	4,81		
Commitment to the Organization 2	Elementary	10	1,82	0,21	0,89
	High School	16	1,95		
	VHS	1	1,67		
	University	4	1,71		

Diversity Analysis of the Dimensions of Commitment to the Organization by Educational Status was made with one-sided analysis of variance and because of F-values indicating the corresponding values of p greater than 0.05; commitment to the organization remain the same regardless of the educational status.

TABLE XI
RESULTS OF DIVERSITY ANALYSIS OF THE DIMENSIONS OF COMMITMENT TO THE ORGANIZATION BY AGE

		N	Mean	F	P
Commitment to the Organization 1	18-25	1	4,78	0,78	0,52
	26-30	6	3,98		
	31-35	11	4,43		
	36 and more	13	4,42		
Commitment to the Organization 2	18-25	1	1,67	2,49	0,08
	26-30	6	2,39		
	31-35	11	1,91		
	36 and more	13	1,60		

According to Table XI, Diversity Analysis of the Dimensions of Commitment to the Organization by Age made with one-sided analysis of variance and because F-values indicate the corresponding values of p greater than 0.05, commitment to the organization remain the same regardless of age.

G. The Relationship Between Leadership Behavior Dimensions and Dimensions of Commitment to the Organization

The relationship between dimensions of leadership behavior and dimensions of commitment to the organization of behavior were tried to determine by correlation analysis. Inner relationships of dimensions of leadership behavior and commitment to the organizational took place in the analysis. The results obtained are given in Table XII.

Hypothesis: There is a relationship between dimensions of Leadership Behaviors and dimensions of commitment to the organization.

TABLE XII

RESULTS OF CORRELATION ANALYSIS BETWEEN DIMENSIONS OF LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR AND DIMENSIONS OF COMMITMENT TO THE ORGANIZATION

	Transformational Leadership	Transactional Leadership	Liberal Leadership	Commitment to the Organization 1	Commitment to the Organization 2
Transformational Leadership	1,00	0,53**	-0,48**	0,31	-0,40*
Transactional Leadership		1,00	0,29	-0,13	0,31
Liberal Leadership			1,00	-0,42*	0,57**
Commitment to the Organization 1				1,00	-0,67**
Commitment to the Organization 2					1,00

** : Significant correlation at 99% confidence interval
* : Significant correlation with 95% confidence interval

According to the result of the correlation analysis, there is a moderate positive significant correlation between transformational leadership and transactional leadership at the level of $R = 0.53$. There is a middle leveled negative correlation between transformational leadership and the liberalization at the level of $R = -0.48$. There is no significant relationship between the transactional leadership and liberal leadership. In the organization while transformational leadership increases transformational leadership arise, but the recognition of freedom declines. There is a inverse correlation between commitment to the Organization dimension 1 and commitment to the Organization dimension 2 with a level of nearly high. Because $R = -0.67$; while commitment to the organization increases commitment to the organization 2 decreases.

When the relationship between leadership behavior and dimensions of commitment to the organization is evaluated, it is seen that there is a middle leveled inverse correlation between transformational leadership and commitment to the organization. While $R = -0.40$ in the table; feature of transformational leadership increases, commitment to the organization 2 is seen to decrease. There is no relationship between transformational leadership and commitment to the organization 1. Dimension of commitment to the organization 1 is regardless of increasing or decreasing transformational leadership property. No significant relationship was found between transactional leadership and commitment to the organization 1 and 2. Increase of decrease in transactional leadership properties, effects commitment. There is an inverse negative relationship between liberal leadership and dimension of commitment to the organization 1. Because $R = -0.42$; in the enterprises where liberal leadership properties increase, dimension of commitment to the organization decreases. But, there is a positive relationship between liberal leadership and dimension of commitment to the organization 2. Because $R = 0.57$; albeit that it is middle leveled, that there is a significant relationship in the same direction. While liberal leadership behavior increases, variables in the dimension of commitment to the organization 2 increase.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, which is made to determine the effect of leadership style on organizational commitment, when the correlation between dimensions of leadership behavior and commitment to the organization; a middle leveled inverse relationship is determined transformational leadership and commitment to the organization. Increase or decrease in transactional leadership properties effects commitment to the organization. While liberal leadership behavior increases, variables belonging to sub-dimension where commitment to the organization is low increases. In the enterprise, for leaders to achieve their goals and to have employees with high level of commitment to the organization, they must adopt transformational leadership approach and prevent the weakening of commitment to the organization.

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